

Microfluidic E-tongue To Diagnose Bovine Mastitis with Milk Samples Using Machine Learning with Decision Tree Models

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Abstract

We report an electronic tongue based on impedance spectroscopy to detect *Staphylococcus aureus* and diagnose bovine mastitis in milk samples. This was achieved with optimized sensing units made with layer-by-layer films and by treating the capacitance data with machine learning algorithms employing decision trees models. These films were made with chitosan, chondroitin sulfate, sericin and gold nanoparticles /sericin, whose molecular-level interaction with *S.aureus* depended on the architecture according to PM IRRAS measurements. The limit of detection in blank milk varied from 3.41 to 2.01 CFU/mL depending on the sensing unit. This sensitivity was complemented with the selectivity provided by combining the electrical responses of the

four sensing units. Indeed, with machine learning it was possible to determine multidimensional calibration spaces (MCS) that could generate rules to explain how the milk samples could be discriminated. With a 7-dimension MCS, distinct *S.aureus* concentrations could be distinguished from possible interferents with a 100% accuracy. In crude milk samples, 94% accuracy was obtained with a 6-dimension MCS in multiclass classification for milk from different udders of a mastitis infected cow, including samples diluted 50 fold, in addition to milk from an infected cows treated with Bronopol and from a healthy cow. It is significant that in a ternary classification with these crude milk samples, a 2-dimension MCS could distinguish between milk from an infected cow, treated with Bronopol and from a healthy cow with 100% accuracy. The combination of electronic tongues and machine learning – as in this proof-of-concept study - is promising for diagnosis of mastitis at a low cost.

Keywords: Mastitis, *S.aureus*, electronic tongue, sensors, impedance spectroscopy, machine learning, multidimensional calibration space,

1) Introduction

Bacterial infections leading to mastitis impose considerable negative impact on global milk production, with annual losses in the US alone estimated at \$ 30 billion[1,2] owing to treating costs of dairy cattle with services from veterinarians, drugs,[3] and slaughter[4]. Much of these losses are due to inflammation of the mammary gland/udder (intramammary inflammation) in cows infected by *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S.aureus*) and *Streptococcus agalactiae*,[5–7] which induce physiological changes in the cows, compromising the quality of milk and volume of production[8]. Several mastitis-causing pathogens are potentially zoonotic, and the antibiotic used in their treatment can generate milk residues[9,10]. A rapid and precise diagnosis of mastitis is therefore essential to reduce financial losses and administration of antibiotics which may lead to bacteria resistance[11]. Bovine mastitis is currently detected through changes in milk properties, udder examination, bacterial culture[12] and ultrasonography[13,14]. Subclinical mastitis, on the other hand, is diagnosed using expensive commercial tests with long detection times, including enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) test[15] and polymerase chain reaction (PCR).[13,16,17] These methods provide diagnosis within a few hours, but with low sensitivity and specificity[18].Therefore, there is an important demand for low-cost methodologies to detect mastitis at an early stage, with high accuracy and a minimum of false positives . This can be achieved with sensors and biosensors within the point-of-care paradigm. Biosensors based on an active layer that incorporates antibodies may provide high sensitivity and selectivity as they interact specifically with bacteria such as *S. aureus*[1,19,20]. A challenge for the use of antibodies includes limited stability for such biosensors.

An alternative to biosensors for detecting bacteria is to employ electronic tongues (e-tongues), whose principle of sample discrimination relies on the global

selectivity concept[21,22]. According to this principle, detection is not made via specific interactions between the sensor-containing materials and the analyte; instead, the electrical responses obtained with an array of sensing units are combined to provide a “finger print” of the liquid under analysis.[23] This pattern recognition strategy in e-tongues requires a suitable choice of sensing units, as they should generate varied electrical responses for a given liquid. E-tongues based on electrochemical methods and electrical impedance spectroscopy have been used in various applications, which include analysis of milk for mastitis diagnosis[24,25], detection of *S.aureus*[26,27], and for monitoring milk freshness.[28] A clear advantage in the use of electronic tongues is in the versatility of materials that can be used in the sensing units; indeed, as biomolecules are not required the overall cost of the tests is reduced and the sensors may be more robust.

In this study, we developed a microfluidic e-tongue to detect *S.aureus* in different types of milk samples and diagnose mastitis via analysis of crude milk. The e-tongue consisted of four sensing units with layer-by-layer (LbL) films[29,30] adsorbed on interdigitated gold electrodes. These films were produced from chitosan (CHT), chondroitin sulfate (CS), sericin (SER) and SER incorporating gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). The choice of these molecular architectures was motivated by two factors. First, CHT/CS films were already proven suitable for e-tongues, including with optimized architecture[19]. The second reason was to exploit gold nanoparticles in the films since enhanced sensitivity is normally achieved by incorporating metallic nanoparticles. The LbL films containing SER had their architecture optimized in this work upon combining various experimental methods: UV-VIS spectroscopy, quartz crystal microbalance (QCM), measurement of contact angle and surface energy, and polarization-modulated infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (PM-IRRAS). High

accuracy in *S.aureus* detection and mastitis diagnosis was achieved in proof-of-concept analysis by treating the impedance data with the multidimensional projection technique referred to as interactive document mapping (IDMAP)[31,32] and the Multidimensional Calibration Space concept.[33] The latter is based on supervised machine learning and the results are displayed in the form of a matrix using ExMatrix[34] to explain the classification with Decision Tree (DT) models[35–37]. A few innovative aspects can be highlighted in this work, most of which are related to the use of machine learning to treat the data.

1) Experimental Procedures

2.1. Microfluidic Chip Preparation

Microfluidic chips manufactured according to Soares et al[38] were functionalized with chitosan ($M_v=87000$ g/mol, from Golden-Shell Biochemical, China), chondroitin sulfate ($M_v = 2.2 \times 10^4$ g/mol, from Solabia, Brazil), Sericin Bombix mori (silkworm) (Sigma Aldrich, USA) and gold nanoparticles modified with Sericin Bombix mori (silkworm) (AuNP-SER). Films with four molecular architectures were deposited on the microfluidic electrodes using the layer-by-layer (LbL)[29] technique: chitosan (CHT)/chondroitin sulfate (CS) (10 bilayers), chitosan (CHT)/chondroitin sulfate (CS) (6 bilayers), chitosan (CHT)/sericin(SER) (8 bilayers) and chitosan (CHT)/AuNP modified with Sericin (AuNP-SER) (8 bilayers). Film fabrication was realized by injecting 1mg/mL CHT solution into the electrode microchannel using a glass syringe (Hamilton) connected to a syringe pump (New Era Pump Syringes) and a flow rate 20 μ L/min. Then, aqueous solutions of chondroitin sulfate (1mg/mL)/sericin (1mg/mL)/AuNP-SER solution (0.2 mmol/L) were injected into the electrode under the same conditions. All the steps above were followed by

washing with ultrapure water to remove non-adsorbed molecules from the electrode. With repetition of these steps, the multilayer films were deposited with different numbers of bilayers.

2.2. Functionalization of AuNPs with Sericin

Sericin *Bombix mori* (silkworm) was used to functionalize gold nanoparticles (AuNP), which were employed in building LbL[29] films with chitosan (CHT). AuNPs were synthesized and functionalized using the following procedures:

- A 0.02 mmol/L NaBH₄ sodium borohydride solution- (reducing agent) (Sigma-Aldrich, USA, 98.0%)- was added to a beaker under constant stirring for 5 min. followed by addition of auric chloride (HAuCl₄) (Sigma-Aldrich, USA, 99.9%) salt, resulting in a slightly reddish solution;
- Steric stabilization was reached by adding Sericin *Bombyx mori* 0.2 mmol/L onto AuNP solution to avoid nanoparticle agglomeration;
- The formation of AuNPs was monitored with UV-vis *in situ* spectroscopy using a HR2000 Ocean optics spectrophotometer, with a solution spectrum taken every 5 min until the signal stabilized.

2.3. Protocols for *S.aureus* Detection.

The *blank* milk used in the experiment was obtained from a healthy cow without mastitis after veterinary evaluation and three negative microbiological tests at one-week intervals. Electrical impedance was used to analyze three sets of milk samples, using a microfluidic electronic tongue consisting of four sensing units, as follows:

- i) Blank milk samples spiked with bacteria were prepared containing *S. aureus* (INCQS 00015 ATCC 25923), diluted in PBS, over an 8 order of magnitude range (1, 10, 10², 10³, 10⁴, 10⁵, 10⁶ and 10⁷ CFU/mL). The contaminated milk samples were injected into the electrode with a flow rate 20 µL/min for 10 min, followed by washing with ultrapure water to remove non-adsorbed molecules. A triplicate was performed for each *S.aureus* concentrations.
- ii) Blank milk samples as in i) but with the added interferents *Salmonella*, lactose, mucin, urea, water and sodium hydroxide to verify possible false positives. The injection procedure was the same as above. A duplicate was performed for each interferent sample.
- iii) Milk from 5 animals was extracted from Embrapa Gado de Leite (Juiz de Fora, MG, Brazil) and Luiz de Queiroz College of Agriculture (ESALQ) (Piracicaba, SP, Brazil) farms, from animals naturally infected with mastitis. The bacterial isolation was made in blood agar plates, followed by biochemical tests to identify the pathogen[39] . These samples can be subdivided into 7 classes: a) milk from a healthy cow (HC); b) milk from the left front mammary quarter (left udder) of an infected cow (LFMQ) ; c) milk from the left front mammary quarter (left udder) of the latter infected cow, diluted 50x (LFMQ50x); d) milk from the right front mammary quarter (right udder) of the another infected cow (RFMQ); e) milk from the right front mammary quarter (right udder) of latter the infected cow, diluted 50x (RFMQ50x); f) milk from the left front

mammary quarter (left udder) of an infected cow, treated with Bronopol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA, $M_w=199.99$ g/mol) (SSCC), with a small somatic cell count (SCC); g) milk from left front mammary quarter (left udder) of another infected cow, treated with Bronopol, with a high count of somatic cells (HSCC). The measurements were performed in a Solartron (model SI 1260 A) in the frequency range from 1 to 10^6 Hz inside a class II type B2 biosafety cabinet for protection against external contamination. Milk composition (in the Support Information) and somatic cell count analysis were performed on Bentley Combi System 2300® electronic equipment. A quintuplicate was performed for each crude milk, except for milk samples with a low somatic cell (SCC) concentration, treated with Bronopol.

2.4. Data Analysis with Information Visualization and Machine Learning Techniques

Electrical impedance spectra (capacitance x frequency), taken with positive and negative *S.aureus* controls, were processed using Projection Explorer Sensors software (PEX-Sensors), which implements the multidimensional projection technique Interactive Document Mapping (IDMAP)[31] and the Parallel Coordinates technique (PC)[40,41]. The first technique calculates the Euclidean distance $\delta(x_i, x_j)$ between the spectra for different *S.aureus* concentrations in the original space $X=\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, and projects them into a lower dimensional space where $Y=\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$ is the position of the visual elements and $d(y_i, y_j)$ is the Euclidean distance in this space. These projections are calculated using the injective function $f: X \rightarrow Y$ that minimizes the term $|\delta(x_i, x_j) - d(f(x_i) - f(x_j))| \forall x_i, x_j \in X$, given by eq. 1

$$S_{IDMAP} = \frac{\delta(x_i, x_j) - \delta_{\min}}{\delta_{\max} - \delta_{\min}} - d(y_i, y_j) \quad (1)$$

where δ_{\max} and δ_{\min} are maximum and minimum Euclidean distances between the data instances. The Parallel Coordinates technique allowed us to identify the frequencies at which a higher distinction can be reached between samples for building calibration curves and determining parameters such as limit of detection (LoD), limit of quantification (LoQ) and sensitivity. The distinction ability in using impedance spectroscopy was calculated using the Silhouette Coefficient (S) defined in eq. (2),

$$S = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(b_i - a_i)}{\max(b_i, a_i)} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the number of samples, \mathbf{a}_i is the average of the calculated Euclidean distances between the i^{th} data point and the data points of all the samples with the same concentration, \mathbf{b}_i is the minimum average Euclidean distances computed between the i^{th} data point and data points of the other samples with different concentrations[32,41,42]. This coefficient varies between -1 and 1, where (S~1) indicates that the clusters are distinct from each other, with (S~0) and (S~-1) indicating that distinction of the clusters is neutral or deleterious, respectively[41,42].

We also created Multidimensional Calibration Spaces (MCS)[43] from the capacitance values and concentrations taken as classes[44], providing interpretability via ExMatrix[45] with Decision Tree models (DT)[46–48]. This was implemented as a Python package (available at <https://pypi.org/project/exmatrix/>) at the Python Package Index (PyPI). An MCS was created for impedance data in four cases: i) blank milk

samples with added *S.aureus* at 9 concentrations (taken as 9 classes[44]); ii) blank milk samples with added *S.aureus* (including the 9 *S.aureus* concentrations) and added interferents for a binary classification (positive - Bac or negative - No Bac); iii) milk samples taken from the left and right udder of a cow with mastitis compared with pure milk (milk from a healthy cow); iv) and milk with high and low somatic cell concentrations, thus representing a ternary classification (Pure Milk - No Bac, Milk Left/Right udder - Bac, and Milk SCC - No Bac). A model selection experiment[37] was performed to choose hyperparameter combinations that maximized the performance (i.e. accuracy) of the DT model through a KFold Cross-Validation[37,49]. The models created with different hyperparameters were evaluated during the KFold Cross-Validation, with the hyperparameters producing the highest average performance being applied to create the final model using the entire dataset. To estimate the average performance of the deployed (final) DT model, a Nested KFold Cross-Validation was executed[50,51] with two KFold Cross-Validation loops (inner and outer). In the inner loop the model hyperparameters are tuned (model selection)[37], while the outer loop is associated with the estimation of model performance[50,51]. These procedures avoid optimistic (overestimation) and biased performances, which are common issues on small datasets[50,51]. MCS allows for interpretability by revealing relationships among capacitances and classes (e.g., concentrations and bacteria presence), while the Nested KFold Cross-Validation method provides a more accurate performance evaluation.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Molecular architectures for the e-tongue sensing units

The e-tongue consisted of four sensing units made of gold microfluidic electrodes coated with CHT/CS (6 bilayers), CHT/CS (10 bilayers), CHT/SER (8 bilayers) and CHT/AuNP-SER (8 bilayers). The optimized time for functionalization of AuNPs with sericin was found to be 175 min, according to the UV-VIS spectra in Figure S1 in the Supporting Information. The buildup of CHT/SER and CHT/AuNP-SER LbL films is illustrated in the UV-VIS spectra of Figures S2, where it is shown that eight is the maximum number of bilayers for a linear growth. The adsorbed mass for each film was estimated from QCM measurements using Sauerbrey equation[52], and the data are given in Figure S3 and Table S1 (Supporting Information). Figure S4 shows that the adsorption of CHT/AuNP-SER and CHT/SER LbL films led to more hydrophilic surfaces with increasing number of bilayers, probably owing to the polar groups NH₂, COOH and O-H from chitosan and sericin. The different surface energies calculated with the Owens-Wendt-Rabel-Kaelble model[53] indicate that the films should exhibit distinct electrical responses, which is favorable for the global selectivity concept of an e-tongue. The adsorption of CHT, SER and AuNPs in the LbL films was confirmed with the PM-IRRAS spectra in Figure S5, whose bands were summarized in Table S2 in the Supporting Information.

3.2. *S.aureus* Detection in Blank Milk Samples

The microfluidic e-tongue made with CHT/CS (6 bilayers), CHT/CS (10 bilayers), CHT/SER (8 bilayers) and CHT/AuNP-SER (8 bilayers) was able to detect *S. aureus* in blank milk at concentrations from 1.0 to 1.0×10^7 CFU/mL using electrical impedance (Z) spectroscopy. Figure 1 show the capacitance spectra for detecting *S.aureus* using the 4 molecular architectures, where a clear distinction of the samples is

Figure 1: Capacitance spectra for sensing units made with (A) CHT/CS (6 bilayers), (B) CHT/CS (10 bilayers), (C) CHT/SER (8 bilayers) and (D) CHT/AuNP-SER (8 bilayers) films used in the e-tongue for detecting *S.aureus*

The combination of the electrical response of the four sensing units in the e-tongue provides a clear discrimination of the different *S.aureus* concentrations, as indicated in the IDMAP[31] plot in Figure 2 where each spectrum is represented as a marker. The data points corresponding to the *S.aureus* samples are placed progressively farther from the control sample (pure milk) as the concentration increases. Some saturation is noted at the highest concentrations (10^6 - 10^7 CFU/mL). Also shown are data for several interferents added to milk, including *Salmonella*. There are no false positives which confirm the suitability of the e-tongue to detect *S.aureus*, with a silhouette coefficient of 0.785. In subsidiary analyses in Figure S6 in the Supporting Information we noted that with CHT/CS 10 bilayers or CHT/SER sensing units it would be possible to distinguish the bacteria samples, but the silhouette coefficient would be a little lower

than for the e-tongue; it would be 0.77 and 0.74 for CHT/CS 10 bilayers or CHT/SER, respectively. With the two other sensing units employed in isolation, false positives would appear for interferents, mainly *Salmonella*. Their silhouette coefficient for discrimination would be 0.36 and 0.43, for CHT/CS (6 bilayers) and CHT/AuNP-SER (8 bilayers), respectively.

Figure 2: IDMAP plot for the capacitance spectra in detecting *S.aureus* in blank milk samples and with added interferents. The measurements were taken with the e-tongue comprising 4 sensing units with different LbL films: CHT/CS (6 bilayers), CHT/CS (10 bilayers), CHT/SER (8 bilayers) and CHT/AuNP-SER (8 bilayers).

With the sensitivity observed above for the sensing units we verified whether calibration curves could be obtained, as it is normally done with sensors in analytical chemistry. Because we had the whole spectra, we employed the Parallel Coordinates

Technique (PC)[41] to analyze the capacitance data and determine the most convenient frequencies for taking the calibration curves. This was done by plotting the data in PC graphs of Figure 3, with the silhouette coefficient being determined for each frequency. Blue boxes refer to high coefficients, whereas the white boxes indicate that the capacitance value in these frequencies do not assist in sample distinguishing; the red boxes mean that the capacitance value is deleterious for distinguishing the samples (low silhouette coefficients)[62]. The large number of blue boxes indicates that the molecular architectures have high selectivity in all spectra regions, which is reflected in the high average S value. The exception occurs for the CHT/CS-10, which presents selectivity only in the electric double layer region, and thus a lower silhouette coefficient.

Figure 3: Parallel Coordinates projection of the capacitance spectra obtained from *S.aureus* detection using layer-by-layer films fabricated with (A) CHT/CS (6 bilayers), (B) CHT/CS (10 bilayers), (C) CHT/SER (8 bilayers) and (D) CHT/AuNP-SER (8 bilayers).

Based on their silhouette coefficients we chose the frequencies at which the calibration curves were to be established for each sensing unit. The frequencies selected were 1 Hz for CHT/CS (6 bilayers), 1000 Hz for CHT/CS (10 bilayers) and CHT/SER (8 bilayers), and 464 Hz for CHT/AuNP-SER (8 bilayers). These calibration curves in Figure S7 (in Support Information) were used to determine the Limit of Detection (LoD) and Limit of Quantification (LoQ) using the IUPAC recommendation[63] in eq. 3 and 4,

$$LoD = \frac{k_D \times SD}{\alpha} \quad (3)$$

$$LoQ = \frac{k_Q \times SD}{\alpha} \quad (4)$$

where SD is the standard deviation in the curves for 10 control samples (0 CFU/mL), α is the slope of the linear part of the calibration curves and k is a constant chosen according to the confidence level ($k_D=3$ and $k_Q=10$). For CHT/CS (6 bilayers), CHT/CS (10 bilayers), CHT/SER (8 bilayers) and CHT/AuNP-SER (8 bilayers) films, we obtained, respectively, LoD of 3.25, 3.41, 2.61 and 2.01 CFU/mL, while the limits of quantification (LoQ) were 10.72, 11.25, 8.61 and 6.63 CFU/mL. These analytical parameters are sufficient to detect *S.aureus*, allowing one to track mastitis in dairy cattle and food contamination. The molecular architectures that constitute the e-tongue were more sensitive than most devices found in the literature[1,20,64–71] and are competitive with the biosensors developed by Soares et. al[19,72] (Table S3 in the Supporting Information). These sensing units have the advantage of not requiring a specific active layer to detect *S. aureus*, which makes the e-tongue cheaper than biosensors. The non-specific interactions between *S.aureus* and the LbL films in sensing units were investigated with PM-IRRAS spectroscopy with the results shown in Figure S8 in the Supporting Information. Worthy of note are the bands due to adsorption of *S.aureus*[73–77], including the 1443-1488 cm^{-1} band assigned to C-H of CH_2 , amide II and amide I bands from membrane proteins at 1543-1565 cm^{-1} and 1645-1667 cm^{-1} , respectively, and 2847-2863 cm^{-1} and 2918-2938 cm^{-1} bands assigned to $\nu\text{C-H}$ from CH_3 and CH_2 , respectively.

3.4. Machine learning applied in *S. aureus* detection

The high sensitivity and distinguishing ability of the e-tongue is promising but there is still the challenge of signals being observed for interferences as in the IDMAP

plot in Figure 2. As expected, the selectivity of the sensing units is limited, despite the distinguishing ability. This limitation can be addressed using supervised machine learning methods which are bound to yield a higher performance in diagnosis. In particular, we decided to use the concept of the multidimensional calibration space (MCS), which provides predictability in addition to classifying the samples. MCS[43] were created with the capacitance spectra in four examples as mentioned in the Methodology section. Each sensing unit of the e-tongue provides the capacitance value at 19 frequencies (1 to 1000000 Hz), resulting in 76 frequencies with the 4 sensors combined (CHT-AuNP-SER, CHT-SER, CHT-CS-6bi, and CHT-CS-10bi). The four (4) resulting calibrations were generated using DT models[37,47], with tuned hyperparameters in model selection experiments[37]. The Nested KFold Cross-Validation procedure was performed with $k_{\text{outer}} = 3$ and $k_{\text{inner}} = 18$ for the Multidimensional Calibration Space (MCS) in Figure 4, with a total of 27 samples among 9 concentrations (3 samples for each concentration). This procedure had 100% accuracy in the e-tongue calibration. The visual representations (ExMatrix)[45] display logic rules extracted from DT models, where rows represent the rules, columns show features and cells correspond to rule predicates. The x-axis shows different capacitance values to different classes (e.g., concentrations and bacteria presence) mapped as colors for the different categories.

Figure 4 displays the ExMatrix[45] for the MCS which illustrates how different *S.aureus* concentrations can be distinguished with the combination of the electrical response for 4 sensing units (i.e. data for the e-tongue). The MCS for each sensing unit are shown in Figure S9 in the Supporting Information. The concentrations were discretized[44] in nine classes: 0, 1, 10, 10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4 , 10^5 , 10^6 , and 10^7 CFU/mL. In the ExMatrix representation, rules (rows) are ordered by concentration class, and the

features (columns) are ordered by importance. The calibration contains 7 dimensions (features), which correspond to the 7 selected among the 76 frequencies (F1 to F1000000 Hz for 4 sensors). The most important feature is F100000 (Hz) for CHT-AuNP-SER (first column) with an importance value of 0.25. The MCS involves at least one frequency (feature/column) from each sensor in the e-tongue. The frequencies F100000 and F1000000 (first and second columns) come from sensor CHT-AuNP-SER, F4 and F100000 (third and fourth columns) from CHT-SER, F100 and F1000 (fifth and sixth columns) from CHT-CS-6bi, and F1000 again (seventh column) from CHT-CS-10bi. Full explanation (i.e. 100% accuracy) of the data is achieved with the minimum number of rules (9, one per concentration class), which indicates a great distinguishing ability when frequencies from different sensors are combined. In most capacitance ranges, except for rule r4 (fourth row) on feature F10000 (Hz) CHT-AuNP-SER (first column), higher values of capacitance (right-most rectangles) tend to be related to higher concentrations. The concentration class 0 (blue), for instance, is defined by small capacitances at F1000 (Hz) CHT-CS-10bi (seventh column). Other noteworthy observations include the need to use only two and three features (i.e. frequencies) to determine concentration classes 1 (orange) and 10 (olive), respectively, while for higher concentrations a larger number of frequencies had to be combined.

Figure 4 - Multidimensional Calibration Space (MCS) via DT model for the e-tongue applied for distinguishing milk samples with various *S.aureus* concentrations. The concentrations discretized resulted in 9 classes (0, 1, 10, 10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4 , 10^5 , 10^6 , and 10^7 CFU/mL). The space has 7 dimensions corresponding to 7 frequencies (features) selected among the 76 available (F1 to F1000000 Hz for 4 sensors). In this ExMatrix representation, logic rules are displayed in a matrix fashion as rows, features as columns, and rule predicates as cells. The rules were ordered by class and coverage, while features were ordered by importance. The rules predicates define ranges (rectangles) in capacitance values distinguishing concentrations classes mapped in different colors. The first column has the most important feature, i.e., F100000 (Hz) CHT-AuNP-SER with an importance value 0.25. The minimum number of rules (9, one per concentration class with maximum coverage) is reached with the selected frequencies. At least one frequency from each sensor in the e-tongue was selected (4 sensors: CHT-AuNP-SER, CHT-SER, CHT-CS-6bi, and CHT-CS-10bi). The average accuracy estimated for the MCS via the DT model is 100%.

The task of identifying *S.aureus* contamination in blank milk, without determining the concentration, was found to be much easier than in the example above, despite the inclusion of data from interferents. The one-dimension MCS in Figure S10 indicates that just one feature is sufficient to detect *S.aureus* presence in the binary classification between positive (Bac) and negative (No Bac) samples. These samples were prepared by adding bacteria at various concentrations in blank milk (Bac) and possible interferent solutions (*Salmonella*, Water, Mucin, Lactose, Urea, and NaOH, without bacteria) (No Bac) to blank milk. The feature used was frequency F2 (Hz) for sensor CHT-SER, and there are only two rules, one for each class. From the matrix in Figure S10 (in support information) one notes that higher capacitances at F2 (Hz) CHT-SER (right-most rectangle in rule r2 on the first row) are associated with class Bac (blue, bacteria present at different concentrations).

3.6. Validation of Mastitis Detection with Real Samples.

To validate the use of the e-tongue in diagnosing mastitis via *S.aureus* detection we employed milk samples collected from 5 different dairy cattle from Embrapa Gado de Leite and ESALQ-USP, some of which had been naturally infected with *S.aureus*.

The samples can be categorized into seven classes, as follows:

- 1) Milk from a healthy cow (HC);
- 2) Milk from the left front mammary quarter (left udder) of an infected cow (LFMQ);
- 3) Milk from the left front mammary quarter (left udder) of the latter infected cow, diluted 50x (LFMQ50x);
- 4) Milk from the right front mammary quarter (right udder) of the another infected cow (RFMQ);
- 5) Milk from the right front mammary quarter (right udder) of latter the infected cow, diluted 50x (RFMQ50x);
- 6) Milk from the left front mammary quarter (left udder) of an infected cow, treated with Bronopol (Sigma-Aldrich, USA, $M_w=199.99$ g/mol), with a small somatic cell count (SSCC);
- 7) Milk from left front mammary quarter (left udder) of another infected cow, treated with Bronopol, with a high count of somatic cells (HSCC).

The IDMAP plot in Figure 5 shows seven clusters for the capacitance data obtained with the e-tongue. Diluted milk samples (3 and 5) have electrical characteristics closer to the control sample (sample 1), indicating a lower concentration of *S.aureus* per volume compared to undiluted samples from the left and right s (samples 2 and 4). Milk samples from the right udder seem to have a lower *S.aureus* concentration than those from the left udder, which should be expected by a visual

inspection of the udders of the infected cow. A high somatic cell indicates but is not a conclusive sign of cow mastitis[78]. Samples 6 and 7 treated with Bronopol did not have bacteria but could be distinguished from the control samples owing to their somatic cells.

Figure 5: IDMAP projection of the capacitance spectra of the e-tongue for analysis of milk collected from cows infected with mastitis. Also included are data from milk of a healthy cow (control) (HC).

The seven classes could be classified at a 94% accuracy estimated with the Nested KFold Cross-Validation method using the 6-dimension MCS displayed in Figure 6. This method was conducted with $k_{\text{outer}} = 5$ and $k_{\text{inner}} = 4$, where 35 samples among 5 classes were used (5 samples per class). The six features corresponded to frequencies with at least one from each sensor, as follows: F464158 (Hz) from sensor CHT-AuNP-SER, F4641 (Hz) and F215443 (Hz) from CHT-SER, F4641 (Hz) and F1000 from CHT-CS-6bi, and F21 (Hz) from CHT-CS-10bi. Two groups are

distinguished with F1000 (Hz) CHT-CS-6bi (sixth column). The first one has smaller capacitances (left-most rectangles) for the classes Milk from Right udder (diluted 50x) (RFMQ50x) (brown), Milk from Left udder (blue) (LFMQ), and Healthy Pure Milk (control) (yellow) (HC). The second one had higher capacitances (right-most rectangles) sorting classes Milk with High SCC + Bronopol (purple) (HSCC), Milk from Right udder (olive) (RFMQ), Milk from Left udder (diluted 50x) (orange) (LFMQ50x), and Milk with Low SCC + Bronopol (pink) (SSCC). The first group is defined by rules r2, r3, and r1 (first three rows). The second group is set by rules r6, r7, r5, and r4 (third to the seventh row), where a subgroup is formed with classes Milk with High SCC + Bronopol (purple) (HSCC) and Milk from Right udder (RFMQ) (olive) having higher values of capacitance at F4641 (Hz) CHT-SER (second column), being different from each other at F464158 (Hz) CHT-AuNP-SER (first column) with higher values for Milk from Right udder (olive) (RFMQ).

In addition to the multiclass analysis above, a 2-dimension MCS was obtained for the ternary classification for positive (Bac) from milk of right and left udders (RFMQ, LFMQ, RFMQ50x and LFMQ50x), positive (no Bac SCC) for milk treated with Bronopol (HSCC), and negative (No Bac) for milk from a healthy cow (HC). The matrix in Figure S11 in the Supporting Information contains three rows for the 3 rules explaining the data, which used two frequencies, viz. F21 (Hz) and F4 (Hz) from sensors CHT-CS-10bi and CHT-SER, respectively. The accuracy of the DT model was 100%.

Figure 6 - Multidimensional Calibration Space (MCS) via DT model for the e-tongue to detect bacteria in milk samples: Milk from healthy cow (control) (HC), Milk from Right udder (diluted 50x) (RFMQ50x), Milk from Left udder (diluted 50x) (LFMQ50x), Milk from Right udder (RFMQ), Milk from Left udder (LFMQ), Milk with Low SCC + Bronopol (SSCC), and Milk with High SCC + Bronopol (HSCC). The space has 6 dimensions, F464158 (Hz) CHT-AuNP-SER, F4641 (Hz) CHT-SER, F4641 (Hz) CHT-CS-6bi, F215443 (Hz) CHT-SER, F21 (Hz) CHT-CS-10bi, and F1000 CHT-CS-6bi. The selected frequencies have equal importance (value of 0.17) and the average accuracy estimated for the MCS via DT model is 94%.

For the MCS in Figure 6, the Nested KFold Cross-Validation procedure was conducted with $k_{\text{outer}} = 5$. Thus, five (5) confusion matrices are obtained, one for each outer fold. Figure S12 in the Support Information shows the matrices, in which a sample belonging to class HC – 'Pure Milk (control)' was misclassified as LFMQ50x (Milk from the left front mammary quarter (left udder) of the latter infected cow, diluted 50x) and RFMQ50x – (Milk from the right front mammary quarter (left udder) of the latter infected cow, diluted 50x) in folds 1 and 3. All samples were classified correctly in folds 2, 4, and 5.

4. Conclusion

The choice of chitosan, chondroitin sulfate, sericin and gold nanoparticles to produce LbL films to coat the interdigitated electrodes was found suitable for generating

a high-performance e-tongue to detect *S. aureus*. This is likely due to the varied electrical responses induced from the different molecular-level interactions between the film-forming materials and *S. aureus*, as indicated in the PM-IRRAS spectra of the LbL films exposed to various milk samples. We observed a high sensitivity for the sensing units, comparable to that of biosensors. The selectivity, however, was not high when the data from a sensing unit were taken in isolation; indeed, the selectivity should be limited as the interactions with *S. aureus* were non-specific. Nevertheless, with the global selectivity principle inherent in e-tongues full discrimination of milk samples could be obtained in various experiments, either using IDMAP or machine learning. With the latter, in particular, multidimensional calibration spaces (MCS) were created which could establish rules to explain the classification of milk samples. Of special relevance was the diagnosis of bovine mastitis with the analysis of milk samples from infected cows.

Using a microfluidic e-tongue for this purpose has several advantages. Only small volumes of milk are necessary; the impedance measurements can be performed with portable spectrometers by technicians with very basic training. The data analysis system with MCS is easily deployable, and therefore the overall approach is promising for point-of-care diagnosis for mastitis and related diseases on farms. Compared with the literature [1,19,20,64–72], the use of machine learning to treat the data of an electronic tongue brings new possibilities to obtain accurate diagnosis without the expensive procedures with clinical analysis. There are important limitations in our study, though, which we acknowledge here. The most important relates to potential challenges with the robustness of the sensing units; when they need to be replaced a new MCS will be required. The results presented here serve as proof-of-concept, but a

larger number of real samples with crude milk and additional potential interferents should be used to fully assess the utility of this approach.

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6. References

- [1] D. Juronen, A. Kuusk, K. Kivirand, A. Rincken, T. Rincken, Immunosensing system for rapid multiplex detection of mastitis-causing pathogens in milk, *Talanta*. 178 (2018) 949–954. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2017.10.043>.
- [2] H. Castañeda Vázquez, S. Jäger, W. Wolter, M. Zschöck, M.A. Castañeda Vazquez, A. El-Sayed, Isolation and identification of main mastitis pathogens in Mexico, *Arq. Bras. Med. Vet. Zootec.* 65 (2013) 377–382. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0102-09352013000200012>.
- [3] S.C. MacDiarmid, Antibacterial drugs used against mastitis in cattle by the systemic route, *New Zealand Veterinary Journal*. 26 (1978) 290–295. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00480169.1978.34574>.
- [4] J. Kvapilík, O. Hanuš, L. Bartoň, M.V. Klimešová, P. Roubal, Mastitis of Dairy Cows and Financial Losses: an Economic Meta-Analysis and Model Calculation, *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science*. 21 (2015) 1092–1105.
- [5] D. Oliveira, A. Borges, M. Simões, Staphylococcus aureus Toxins and Their Molecular Activity in Infectious Diseases, *Toxins*. 10 (2018) 252. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins10060252>.

- [6] G. Keefe, Update on Control of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus agalactiae* for Management of Mastitis, *Veterinary Clinics of North America: Food Animal Practice*. 28 (2012) 203–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cvfa.2012.03.010>.
- [7] K. Sharun, K. Dhama, R. Tiwari, M.B. Gugjoo, Mohd. Iqbal Yattoo, S.K. Patel, M. Pathak, K. Karthik, S.K. Khurana, R. Singh, B. Puvvala, Amarpal, R. Singh, K.P. Singh, W. Chaicumpa, Advances in therapeutic and managemental approaches of bovine mastitis: a comprehensive review, *Veterinary Quarterly*. 41 (2021) 107–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01652176.2021.1882713>.
- [8] M.A. Helayel, A.T. Ramos, S. de P. Lopes, I.M. da Cunha, P.C.A.R. da Silva, R.P.R. Moutinho, V. de A.N. Carvalho, S.A. Caldas, Rupture of the mammary vein in a Holstein cow with mastitis and udder edema: case report, *Braz. J. Vet. Med.* 40 (2018) e094118. <https://doi.org/10.29374/2527-2179.bjvm094118>.
- [9] S.N. Garcia, B.I. Osburn, J.S. Cullor, A one health perspective on dairy production and dairy food safety, *One Health*. 7 (2019) 100086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2019.100086>.
- [10] C.J. McDaniel, D.M. Cardwell, R.B. Moeller, G.C. Gray, Humans and Cattle: A Review of Bovine Zoonoses, Vector-Borne and Zoonotic Diseases. 14 (2014) 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1089/vbz.2012.1164>.
- [11] V. Krömker, S. Leimbach, Mastitis treatment-Reduction in antibiotic usage in dairy cows, *Reprod Dom Anim*. 52 (2017) 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rda.13032>.
- [12] A. Ashraf, M. Imran, Diagnosis of bovine mastitis: from laboratory to farm, *Trop Anim Health Prod*. 50 (2018) 1193–1202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11250-018-1629-0>.
- [13] A. El-Sayed, W. Awad, N.-E. Abdou, H. Castañeda Vázquez, Molecular biological tools applied for identification of mastitis causing pathogens, *International Journal of Veterinary Science and Medicine*. 5 (2017) 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijvsm.2017.08.002>.
- [14] V. Perreten, A. Endimiani, A. Thomann, J.R.K. Wipf, A. Rossano, M. Bodmer, A. Raemy, K.A. Sannes-Lowery, D.J. Ecker, R. Sampath, R.A. Bonomo, Evaluation of PCR electrospray-ionization mass spectrometry for rapid molecular diagnosis of bovine mastitis, *Journal of Dairy Science*. 96 (2013) 3611–3620. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2012-6124>.
- [15] S. Wu, N. Duan, H. Gu, L. Hao, H. Ye, W. Gong, Z. Wang, A Review of the Methods for Detection of *Staphylococcus aureus* Enterotoxins, *Toxins*. 8 (2016) 176. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins8070176>.
- [16] Y. Mora-Hernández, E. Vera Murguía, J. Stinenbosch, P. Hernández Jauregui, J.M. van Dijl, G. Buist, Molecular typing and antimicrobial resistance profiling of 33 mastitis-related *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates from cows in the Comarca Lagunera region of Mexico, *Sci Rep*. 11 (2021) 6912. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-86453-2>.
- [17] A. Thomas, S. Chothe, M. Byukusenge, T. Mathews, T. Pierre, S. Kariyawasam, E. Luley, S. Kuchipudi, B. Jayarao, Prevalence and distribution of multilocus sequence types of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from bulk tank milk and cows with mastitis in Pennsylvania, *PLoS ONE*. 16 (2021) e0248528. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248528>.
- [18] Y. Nagasawa, Y. Kiku, K. Sugawara, N. Yabusaki, K. Oono, K. Fujii, T. Suzuki, K. Maehana, T. Hayashi, Rapid *Staphylococcus aureus* Detection From Clinical Mastitis Milk by Colloidal Gold Nanoparticle-Based Immunochromatographic Strips, *Front. Vet. Sci*. 6 (2020) 504. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00504>.

- [19] A.C. Soares, J.C. Soares, V.C. Rodrigues, O.N. Oliveira, L.H. Capparelli Mattoso, Controlled molecular architectures in microfluidic immunosensors for detecting *Staphylococcus aureus*., *Analyst*. 145 (2020) 6014–6023. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0AN00714E>.
- [20] D. Peedel, T. Rinken, Rapid biosensing of *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria in milk, *Anal. Methods*. 6 (2014) 2642. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3ay42036a>.
- [21] K. Toko, A taste sensor, *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 9 (1998) 1919–1936. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-0233/9/12/001>.
- [22] A. Riul, D.S. dos Santos, K. Wohnrath, R. Di Tommazo, A.C.P.L.F. Carvalho, F.J. Fonseca, O.N. Oliveira, D.M. Taylor, L.H.C. Mattoso, Artificial Taste Sensor: Efficient Combination of Sensors Made from Langmuir–Blodgett Films of Conducting Polymers and a Ruthenium Complex and Self-Assembled Films of an Azobenzene-Containing Polymer, *Langmuir*. 18 (2002) 239–245. <https://doi.org/10.1021/la011017d>.
- [23] A. Riul Jr., C.A.R. Dantas, C.M. Miyazaki, O.N. Oliveira Jr., Recent advances in electronic tongues, *Analyst*. 135 (2010) 2481. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c0an00292e>.
- [24] T. Mottram, A. Rudnitskaya, A. Legin, J.L. Fitzpatrick, P.D. Eckersall, Evaluation of a novel chemical sensor system to detect clinical mastitis in bovine milk, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*. 22 (2007) 2689–2693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2006.11.006>.
- [25] F. Winquist, R. Bjorklund, C. Krantz-Rülcker, I. Lundström, K. Östergren, T. Skoglund, An electronic tongue in the dairy industry, *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*. 111–112 (2005) 299–304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2005.05.003>.
- [26] R. Al Ramahi, A.N. Zaid, N. Abu-Khalaf, Evaluating the potential use of electronic tongue in early identification and diagnosis of bacterial infections, *IDR*. Volume 12 (2019) 2445–2451. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S213938>.
- [27] A. Wadehra, P.S. Patil, Application of electronic tongues in food processing, *Anal. Methods*. 8 (2016) 474–480. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5AY02724A>.
- [28] Z. Wei, J. Wang, X. Zhang, Monitoring of quality and storage time of unsealed pasteurized milk by voltammetric electronic tongue, *Electrochimica Acta*. 88 (2013) 231–239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2012.10.042>.
- [29] K. Ariga, E. Ahn, M. Park, B. Kim, Layer-by-Layer Assembly: Recent Progress from Layered Assemblies to Layered Nanoarchitectonics, *Chem. Asian J.* 14 (2019) 2553–2566. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asia.201900627>.
- [30] K. Ariga, Progress in Molecular Nanoarchitectonics and Materials Nanoarchitectonics, *Molecules*. 26 (2021) 1621. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26061621>.
- [31] R. Minghim, F.V. Paulovich, A. de Andrade Lopes, Content-based text mapping using multi-dimensional projections for exploration of document collections, in: R.F. Erbacher, J.C. Roberts, M.T. Gröhn, K. Börner (Eds.), San Jose, CA, 2006: p. 60600S. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.650880>.
- [32] F.V. Paulovich, M.L. Moraes, R.M. Maki, M. Ferreira, O.N. Oliveira Jr., M.C.F. de Oliveira, Information visualization techniques for sensing and biosensing, *Analyst*. 136 (2011) 1344. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c0an00822b>.
- [33] M.P. Neto, A.C. Soares, O.N. Oliveira, F.V. Paulovich, Machine Learning Used to Create a Multidimensional Calibration Space for Sensing and Biosensing Data, *BCSJ*. 94 (2021) 1553–1562. <https://doi.org/10.1246/bcsj.20200359>.
- [34] M.P. Neto, F.V. Paulovich, Explainable Matrix - Visualization for Global and Local Interpretability of Random Forest Classification Ensembles, *IEEE Trans.*

- Visual. Comput. Graphics. 27 (2021) 1427–1437. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2020.3030354>.
- [35] L. Breiman, ed., *Classification and regression trees*, 1. CRC Press repr, Chapman & Hall/CRC, Boca Raton, Fla., 1998.
- [36] P.-N. Tan, M. Steinbach, V. Kumar, *Introduction to data mining*, 1st ed, Pearson Addison Wesley, Boston, 2006.
- [37] G. James, D. Witten, T. Hastie, R. Tibshirani, *An Introduction to Statistical Learning*, Springer New York, New York, NY, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-7138-7>.
- [38] A.C. Soares, J.C. Soares, V.C. Rodrigues, H.D.M. Follmann, L.M.R.B. Arantes, A.C. Carvalho, M.E. Melendez, J.H.T.G. Fregnani, R.M. Reis, A.L. Carvalho, O.N. Oliveira, Microfluidic-Based Genosensor To Detect Human Papillomavirus (HPV16) for Head and Neck Cancer, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*. 10 (2018) 36757–36763. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b14632>.
- [39] S.P. Oliver, M.J. Lewis, B.E. Gillespie, H.H. Downlen, E. Jaenicke, R.K. Roberts, *Microbiological procedures for the diagnosis of bovine udder infection and determination of milk quality*, 4th ed., National Mastitis Council, Verona, 2004.
- [40] F.V. Paulovich, M.L. Moraes, R.M. Maki, M. Ferreira, O.N. Oliveira Jr., M.C.F. de Oliveira, Information visualization techniques for sensing and biosensing, *Analyst*. 136 (2011) 1344. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c0an00822b>.
- [41] A. Inselberg, B. Dimsdale, Parallel coordinates: a tool for visualizing multi-dimensional geometry, in: *Proceedings of the First IEEE Conference on Visualization: Visualization '90*, IEEE Comput. Soc. Press, San Francisco, CA, USA, 1990: pp. 361–378. <https://doi.org/10.1109/VISUAL.1990.146402>.
- [42] J.C. Soares, F.M. Shimizu, A.C. Soares, L. Caseli, J. Ferreira, O.N. Oliveira, Supramolecular Control in Nanostructured Film Architectures for Detecting Breast Cancer, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*. 7 (2015) 11833–11841. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.5b03761>.
- [43] M.P. Neto, A.C. Soares, O.N. Oliveira, F. V. Paulovich, Machine Learning Used to Create a Multidimensional Calibration Space for Sensing and Biosensing Data, *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Japan*. (2021) bcsj.20200359. <https://doi.org/10.1246/bcsj.20200359>.
- [44] R. Salman, V. Kecman, Regression as classification, in: *2012 Proceedings of IEEE Southeastcon, 2012*: pp. 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SECon.2012.6196887>.
- [45] M.P. Neto, F. V. Paulovich, Explainable matrix - Visualization for global and local interpretability of random forest classification ensembles, *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*. 27 (2021) 1427–1437. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2020.3030354>.
- [46] L. Breiman, J. Friedman, C.J. Stone, R.A. Olshen, *Classification and Regression Trees*, Taylor & Francis, 1984.
- [47] P.-N. Tan, M. Steinbach, V. Kumar, *Introduction to Data Mining*, (First Edition), Addison-Wesley Longman Publishing Co., Inc., USA, 2005.
- [48] G. James, D. Witten, T. Hastie, R. Tibshirani, *An Introduction to Statistical Learning: with Applications in R*, Springer New York, 2014.
- [49] C.S. Mellish, ed., *Proceedings of the Fourteenth International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Morgan Kaufmann, San Mateo, Calif, 1995.
- [50] S. Varma, R. Simon, Bias in error estimation when using cross-validation for model selection, *BMC Bioinformatics*. 7 (2006) 91. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-7-91>.

- [51] I. Tsamardinos, A. Rakhshani, V. Lagani, Performance-Estimation Properties of Cross-Validation-Based Protocols with Simultaneous Hyper-Parameter Optimization, in: A. Likas, K. Blekas, D. Kalles (Eds.), *Artificial Intelligence: Methods and Applications*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2014: pp. 1–14. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-07064-3_1.
- [52] G. Sauerbrey, Verwendung von Schwingquarzen zur Wägung dünner Schichten und zur Mikrowägung, *Z. Physik.* 155 (1959) 206–222. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01337937>.
- [53] D.K. Owens, R.C. Wendt, Estimation of the surface free energy of polymers, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 13 (1969) 1741–1747. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.1969.070130815>.
- [54] V.F. Lvovich, *Impedance spectroscopy: applications to electrochemical and dielectric phenomena*, Wiley, Hoboken, N.J., 2012.
- [55] E. Barsoukov, J.R. Macdonald, *Impedance spectroscopy theory, experiment, and applications.*, Wiley-Interscience, Hoboken, N.J., 2005. <http://site.ebrary.com/id/10114201> (accessed June 22, 2021).
- [56] D.M. Taylor, A.G. Macdonald, AC admittance of the metal/insulator/electrolyte interface, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 20 (1987) 1277–1283. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/20/10/010>.
- [57] A.K. Yedluri, D.K. Kulurumotlakatla, S. Sangaraju, I.M. Obaidat, H.-J. Kim, Facile synthesis of novel and highly efficient CoNi₂S₄-Ni(OH)₂ nanosheet arrays as pseudocapacitive-type electrode material for high-performance electrochemical supercapacitors, *Journal of Energy Storage.* 31 (2020) 101623. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2020.101623>.
- [58] Y. Anil Kumar, H.-J. Kim, Preparation and electrochemical performance of NiCo₂O₄@NiCo₂O₄ composite nanoplates for high performance supercapacitor applications†, *New J. Chem.* 42 (2018) 19971–19978. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8NJ05401K>.
- [59] M.R. Pallavolu, Y. Anil Kumar, G. Mani, R.A. Alshgari, M. Ouladsmame, S.W. Joo, Facile fabrication of novel heterostructured tin disulfide (SnS₂)/tin sulfide (SnS)/N-CNO composite with improved energy storage capacity for high-performance supercapacitors, *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry.* 899 (2021) 115695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelechem.2021.115695>.
- [60] M. Xu, Z. Gao, Q. Wei, G. Chen, D. Tang, Hemin/G-quadruplex-based DNAzyme concatamers for in situ amplified impedimetric sensing of copper(II) ion coupling with DNAzyme-catalyzed precipitation strategy, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics.* 74 (2015) 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2015.05.056>.
- [61] Z. Qiu, D. Tang, J. Shu, G. Chen, D. Tang, Enzyme-triggered formation of enzyme-tyramine concatamers on nanogold-functionalized dendrimer for impedimetric detection of Hg(II) with sensitivity enhancement, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics.* 75 (2016) 108–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2015.08.026>.
- [62] J.C. Soares, A.C. Soares, V. da C. Rodrigues, P.R.A. Oiticica, P.A. Raymundo-Pereira, J.L. Bott-Neto, L.A. Buscaglia, L. Castro, L.C. Ribas, L. Scabini, L.C. Brazaca, D. Correa, L.H. Mattoso, M.C. Ferreira de Oliveira, A.C.P.L.F. de Carvalho, E. Carrilho, O.M. Bruno, M.E. Melendez, O. Novais Oliveira Jr., Detection of a SARS-CoV-2 sequence with genosensors using data analysis based on information visualization and machine learning techniques, *Mater. Chem. Front.* (2021) 10.1039/D1QM00665G. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1QM00665G>.
- [63] L.A. Currie, Nomenclature in evaluation of analytical methods including detection and quantification capabilities (IUPAC Recommendations 1995), *Pure and*

- Applied Chemistry. 67 (1995) 1699–1723. <https://doi.org/10.1351/pac199567101699>.
- [64] F. Jia, N. Duan, S. Wu, X. Ma, Y. Xia, Z. Wang, X. Wei, Impedimetric aptasensor for *Staphylococcus aureus* based on nanocomposite prepared from reduced graphene oxide and gold nanoparticles, *Microchim Acta*. 181 (2014) 967–974. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00604-014-1195-8>.
- [65] H. Wang, Y. Xiu, Y. Chen, L. Sun, L. Yang, H. Chen, X. Niu, Electrochemical immunosensor based on an antibody-hierarchical mesoporous SiO₂ for the detection of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *RSC Adv.* 9 (2019) 16278–16287. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9RA00907H>.
- [66] D. Wilson, E.M. Materón, G. Ibáñez-Redín, R.C. Faria, D.S. Correa, O.N. Oliveira, Electrical detection of pathogenic bacteria in food samples using information visualization methods with a sensor based on magnetic nanoparticles functionalized with antimicrobial peptides, *Talanta*. 194 (2019) 611–618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2018.10.089>.
- [67] N. Idil, M. Bakhshpour, I. Perçin, B. Mattiasson, Whole Cell Recognition of *Staphylococcus aureus* Using Biomimetic SPR Sensors, *Biosensors*. 11 (2021) 140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios11050140>.
- [68] J. Cui, M. Zhou, Y. Li, Z. Liang, Y. Li, L. Yu, Y. Liu, Y. Liang, L. Chen, C. Yang, A New Optical Fiber Probe-Based Quantum Dots Immunofluorescence Biosensors in the Detection of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.* 11 (2021) 665241. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2021.665241>.
- [69] R. Cai, Z. Zhang, H. Chen, Y. Tian, N. Zhou, A versatile signal-on electrochemical biosensor for *Staphylococcus aureus* based on triple-helix molecular switch, *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*. 326 (2021) 128842. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2020.128842>.
- [70] G.A. Zelada-Guillén, J.L. Sebastián-Avila, P. Blondeau, J. Riu, F.X. Rius, Label-free detection of *Staphylococcus aureus* in skin using real-time potentiometric biosensors based on carbon nanotubes and aptamers, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*. 31 (2012) 226–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2011.10.021>.
- [71] C.-W. Lee, H.-Y. Chang, J.-K. Wu, F.-G. Tseng, Ultra-sensitive electrochemical detection of bacteremia enabled by redox-active gold nanoparticles (raGNPs) in a nano-sieving microfluidic system (NS-MFS), *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*. 133 (2019) 215–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2019.03.040>.
- [72] Z. Gu, A. Fu, L. Ye, K. Kuerban, Y. Wang, Z. Cao, Ultrasensitive Chemiluminescence Biosensor for Nuclease and Bacterial Determination Based on Hemin-Encapsulated Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles, *ACS Sens.* 4 (2019) 2922–2929. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.9b01303>.
- [73] N.B. Colthup, L.H. Daly, S.E. Wiberley, Introduction to infrared and Raman spectroscopy, 3rd ed, Academic Press, Boston, 1990.
- [74] A. Wieçkowski, C. Korzeniewski, B. Braunschweig, Vibrational Spectroscopy at Electrified Interfaces, 2013. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:101:1-201502084436> (accessed June 22, 2021).
- [75] A. Barth, Infrared spectroscopy of proteins, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Bioenergetics*. 1767 (2007) 1073–1101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbabi.2007.06.004>.
- [76] T. Grunert, M. Wenning, M.S. Barbagelata, M. Fricker, D.O. Sordelli, F.R. Buzzola, M. Ehling-Schulz, Rapid and Reliable Identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* Capsular Serotypes by Means of Artificial Neural Network-Assisted

- Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy, *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*. 51 (2013) 2261–2266. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.00581-13>.
- [77] V. Erukhimovitch, M. Talyshinsky, Y. Souprun, M. Huleihel, Use of Fourier transform infrared microscopy for the evaluation of drug efficiency, *J. Biomed. Opt.* 11 (2006) 064009. <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.2397554>.
- [78] F.N. Souza, A.F. Cunha, D.L.S.O. Rosa, M.A.V. Brito, A.S. Guimarães, L.C. Mendonça, G.N. Souza, A.P. Lage, M.G. Blagitz, A.M.M.P.D. Libera, M.B. Heinemann, M.M.O.P. Cerqueira, Somatic cell count and mastitis pathogen detection in composite and single or duplicate quarter milk samples, *Pesq. Vet. Bras.* 36 (2016) 811–818. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0100-736x2016000900004>.